

Relational Unification of Bosonic and Fermionic Fields: Exchange Statistics and Emergent Pauli Exclusion on Minkowski-Like Spaces

Oded Shor^{1,3†}, Felix Benninger^{1,2,3†}, Abraham Weizman^{1,3,5,6},
Andrei Khrennikov^{4*†}

¹Felsenstein Medical Research Centre, Petach Tikva, Israel.

²Department of Neurology, Rabin Medical Centre, Petach Tikva, Israel.

³Faculty of Medicine, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel.

⁴Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Technology, Linnaeus University, Vaxjö, Sweden.

⁵Sackler Faculty of Medicine, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel.

⁶Geha Mental Health Center, Petach Tikva, Israel.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): andrei.khrennikov@lnu.se;

†These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Dendrographic Holographic Theory (DHT) is a purely relational theory of information in which the primitive elements are events, and physical description is defined by an observer's dendrogram: a hierarchical tree of binary questions that distinguishes events only through operationally accessible relations. The core postulate is an epistemic form of Leibniz's Principle of the Identity of Indiscernibles: if two states of affairs cannot be distinguished by any admissible measurement for a given observer, they are identified for that observer. From each dendrogram we construct a views distribution over relational distances and define a one-particle wavefunction from that distribution; many distinct relational configurations can therefore map to the same distribution and the same wavefunction, so a particle is naturally an equivalence class of dendrograms sharing the same wavefunction. We then study two-particle sectors by embedding a pair of finite dendrograms into a host context consisting of one or two larger dendrograms, allowing both equal-host and distinct-host comparisons and accommodating a range of size relations. When neither host can be embedded into the other, the host pair is space-like separated in a Minkowski-like parameter space, so exchange signatures arise purely from the relative organization of the embedded structures rather than from causal

nesting. Our simulations show that bosonic versus fermionic exchange behaviour is not an intrinsic label of the embedded inputs, but an emergent invariant of the composite relational wiring diagram linking two, often non-relationally closed, information sets through cross-host correlations, reproducing exclusion-like and pile-up behaviour without postulating the Pauli principle. In this sense, DHT offers a unifying perspective on bosonic and fermionic fields: both arise from the same underlying relational degrees of freedom, and boson–fermion conversion corresponds to operations that break or restore relational closure, by changing host choice and embedding pattern, while leaving the one-particle state fixed—an analogue of supersymmetric unification that does not require a new particle spectrum. This suggests a unification of matter and forces at the level of relational organization without introducing new particles and while remaining compatible with a Minkowski-like spacetime encoding.

Keywords: relational information, dendrograms, p-adic topology, exchange symmetry, bosons, fermions, Pauli exclusion principle, Minkowski-like spaces

1 Introduction

Dendrographic Holographic Theory (DHT) is a single-postulate theory of relational information, developed through a series of studies [1–7]. It proposes a relational–event–observational approach to physics and, more broadly, to natural science [8, 9]. The foundational starting is the adherence to Leibniz principle, either epistemically or at the infinite as an ontic principle. [10], The empiricist case is in the spirit close to Mach’s interpretation: “If we are unable to distinguish two states of affairs by any scientific means, then science ought to regard them as identical and take no notice of the difference” [11].

Leibniz’s Principle, or the Principle of the Identity of Indiscernibles (PII), is usually stated as follows: if, for every property P , object x has P if and only if object y has P , then x is identical to y . Informally, if x and y are truly distinct, there must exist at least one property that differentiates them. Historically, this principle served as an ontic tool in Leibniz’s relational metaphysics, in particular for distinguishing between monads [10].

We should note that, in quantum mechanics, we very often treat systems or particles as *perfectly indistinguishable* in a highly idealized — and in some respects artificial — way, without taking into account the full range of properties the particles might possess or the rich relational structure in which they are embedded. The indistinguishability postulate is usually imposed as a constraint on the formalism from the outset, rather than derived from a complete inventory of physically relevant properties [12].

From this perspective, Although, the Leibniz/PII connection has been pursued extensively in the philosophy of physics, it is less visible in mainstream textbook and ‘working physicist’ presentations of indistinguishability [13, 14]. this stands in contradiction to the early developers of quantum theory that were deeply influenced

by Mach’s relational (which is in a sense the empiricist version of PII) and anti-metaphysical philosophy [15–17]. A genuinely Leibnizian/Machian reading would force us to ask which properties and relations are being suppressed when we declare two particles “indistinguishable,” and whether the resulting idealization really earns the right to ignore any possible Leibnizian differences, rather than merely stipulating them away by definition.

One simple example is the usual derivation of Pauli’s exclusion principle and the way we talk about fermions and bosons. In very plain words, the formalism tells us:

1. Take two electrons and assume they are “identical” or “indistinguishable.”
2. Then label them with their space–time positions and write a two-particle wavefunction $\psi(x_1, x_2)$, where x_1 is “electron 1” and x_2 is “electron 2.”
3. Now look at the “exchanged” wavefunction $\psi(x_2, x_1)$ and say: for fermions we must have $\psi(x_2, x_1) = -\psi(x_1, x_2)$, and for bosons we must have $\psi(x_2, x_1) = \psi(x_1, x_2)$.

In the fermionic case we explicitly say that the two expressions are *not* identical: the minus sign is taken to mean that we have two different composite states, and that this difference is physically meaningful (it is exactly what leads to Pauli’s exclusion principle) [18]. So in the end we talk as if there are two distinguishable composite states, even though we started by saying that the two electrons themselves are indistinguishable. But the labels were already there from the beginning: as soon as we wrote x_1 and x_2 , we had “the electron at x_1 ” and “the electron at x_2 ,” and by a Leibnizian (and Machian) reading these are already distinguished by their relational properties.

The bosonic case is a bit different in style. Here the symmetric wavefunction makes the two composite states before and after the exchange look exactly the same in the formalism, so we are told we “cannot distinguish” them. But once we have written different space–time labels x_1 and x_2 for the two bosons, we still know which one was sent where in the exchange move.

From this angle, it is all the more striking that, although a broadly Machian perspective clearly influenced many of the originators of quantum mechanics, the mature formalism seems to take a noticeable detour away from Mach’s own demands. Mach’s slogan was to avoid building one’s ontology out of distinctions that can never, even in principle, show up in experience, and this operational attitude is often invoked to justify talk of “indistinguishable particles.” Yet in practice, the term *indistinguishable* is frequently used in a way that is driven more by the needs of the formalism than by a careful Leibniz–Mach inventory of properties and relations.

In DHT, we adopt an explicitly epistemic reading of this principle. The basic objects are events, and the relevant information is relational and observer-dependent: it concerns how events are distinguished (or not) through measurement. A single, isolated measurement about one event carries no meaning on its own; its significance arises only through comparison with measurements of other events. According to the epistemic Leibniz principle, if a given observer cannot, by any operationally accessible criterion, distinguish between the measurements corresponding to two distinct events, then—for that observer—those events are to be treated as identical. It is important to note, however, that this more pragmatic epistemic reinterpretation introduces additional

postulates, such as the existence of observers and measurements (or “sensations,” in Mach’s terminology [11]).

Formally, DHT is grounded in p -adic topology, governed by a p -adic ultrametric, and it extracts relational information from p -adic tree structures known as dendrograms. An observer distinguishes among events by posing inquiries—often idealized as yes/no questions—that can be represented as a branching tree resembling a decision tree. The resulting dendrogram encodes how observations are related: events that yield longer sequences of identical answers occupy branches with longer shared paths, and are therefore “closer” in the induced metric.

In the limit of infinitely many events, the relational structure of these distinctions is represented by an infinite p -adic tree, with each vertex having $p > 1$ outgoing edges. This tree carries both an algebraic structure and a natural topology, corresponding to the p -adic number field Q_p [19]. In a p -adic ultrametric space, all triangles are isosceles, a consequence of the strong triangle inequality. Distances between two branches depend only on the depth of their common ancestor: a deeper shared root corresponds to a shorter distance (that is, more similar answers to the series of “questions”). Open and closed balls in this space are defined as :

$$B_-(R; a) = \{x : r_p(a, x) < R\}, \quad B(R; a) = \{x : r_p(a, x) \leq R\},$$

where

$$r_p(a, x) = |a - x|_p$$

is the p -adic distance between the points a and x .

The connection between DHT and p -adic/ultrametric analysis also resonates with several developments in theoretical physics.[20–31] In particular, ultrametric structures have long served as effective tools for modeling complexity and disorder, from spin-glass theory to broader disordered systems.[20, 24, 26, 32] Since generic tree-induced distances are ultrametric, the state spaces generated by dendrogramic organization naturally inherit an ultrametric topology, aligning DHT with this well-developed mathematical–physical toolkit.[20, 26]

In this framework, the dendrogram itself furnishes a p -adic ultrametric on events. This ultrametric structure arises directly from the epistemic Leibniz principle and requires no additional geometric background. In this way, the epistemic Leibniz principle leads directly to a Machian form of epistemic relationism: objects (events) are characterized solely by their relational profile within the tree. Background independence, in the sense familiar from shape dynamics, loop quantum gravity, spin foam models, and causal set theory, then emerges not as an extra assumption but as a consequence of endorsing the Leibniz principle along with its structural p -adic tree representation.[33–37] Unlike in shape dynamics or Brans–Dicke theory, where aspects of relationism and background independence are posited, in DHT these features arise intrinsically from the underlying dendrogramic construction.[33, 34, 38]

A dendrogram thus takes the form of a finite tree and serves as an observer’s epistemic representation of reality (which is, by construction, observer-dependent; see Appendix A.1). Such finite trees are built in four epistemic steps: (i) data collection; (ii) hierarchical clustering of the data; (iii) construction of a cluster tree; and (iv)

dendrogram representation of relations, where a longer shared path corresponds to a closer relationship between events according to chosen metrics (Fig. 1).

In our previous and this study, we employ the following equation to facilitate our analysis: The representation of a dendrogram branch, denoted as $edge_i$, can be expressed as the sum of a series:

$$edge_i = \sum_{j=0}^k a_j p^j, \quad a_j \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}. \quad (1.1)$$

Throughout this study, we will use $p = 2$ and thus

$$a_j = 0, 1 \quad (1)$$

Here, a_j represents the binary digit at position j , with possible values of 0 or 1. We now introduce the concept of the monna map conversion of an edge to event, denoted as $event_i$, is computed using the formula:

$$event_i = \sum_{j=0}^k a_j p^{-j-1}, \quad a_j \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}. \quad (1.2)$$

Again, throughout this study, we will use $p = 2$ and thus $a_j \in \{0, 1\}$

where a_j represents the binary digits (0 or 1) in the 2 -adic expansion of the dendrogram branch, and k is the maximum ball level of the dendrogram.

By applying this Monna map conversion, we represent the edges as rational numbers on the continuous interval $[0,1]$. This conversion preserves the precise relations between the edges, ensuring that the inherent structure and ordering within the dendrogram branches are maintained. Furthermore, we introduced the metric q_{ik} , which represents the absolute difference between two events,

$$q_{ik} = |event_i - event_k|. \quad (1.3)$$

1.1 Dendrograms as question-configurations and induced sub-configurations

A dendrogram is an ordered decision tree whose branching nodes represent fundamental “questions” (relational primitives), and whose leaves represent branching outcomes Fig. 1 . The tree is naturally embedded in the p -adic field via its p -adic expansions.

To describe *partial* configurations of questions, we restrict a larger (“global”) dendrogram T to a subset of leaves $S \subseteq L(T)$. The corresponding partial decision structure is the *contracted induced subtree*

$$\text{Ind}_T(S),$$

defined as the minimal rooted subtree of T spanning exactly the leaves in S , with all degree-2 internal vertices contracted. This produces a smaller dendrogram inheriting the left–right order (and hence the p -adic placement of branching nodes) from T . This

restriction implements the inducement, out of context, the same $\text{Ind}_T(S)$ (up to order-preserving isomorphism) to distinct set of events meaning, relationally, these different sets of events are indistinguishable at this level, consistent with earlier numerical observations [1, 2, 4, 5]

1.1.1 Exact induced containment (“has-it” vs. “doesn’t-have-it”).

A smaller dendrogram T_{small} is *exactly induced-contained* in a larger dendrogram T_{big} iff there exists a subset $S \subseteq L(T_{\text{big}})$ such that

$$\text{Ind}_{T_{\text{big}}}(S) = T_{\text{small}}.$$

In this “has-it” case, containment metrics attain their extremal values,

$$d_{\text{inc}}(T_{\text{small}}, T_{\text{big}}) = 0, \quad \text{Match}(T_{\text{small}}, T_{\text{big}}) = 1,$$

so $1 - \text{Match} = 0$. If no such subset exists (the “doesn’t-have-it” case), the metrics become non-extremal and detect failure of induced containment:

$$d_{\text{inc}} > 0, \quad \text{Match} < 1,$$

and in the strongest non-containment regime an insertion-only inclusion distance is taken to be infinite (∞). Thus, $\text{Ind}_T(S)$ both represents a coarse-grained equivalence class of smaller sets of event histories and provides a precise criterion for when a larger dendrogram does (or does not) realize a given lower-level relational question-structure as one of its minimally spanned sub-configurations.

1.2 Short overview of recent results

This subsection is intentionally a high-level overview meant to orient the reader before the theoretical and empirical results, which rely on analytical results developed in our earlier work. For completeness, a more detailed overview is also provided in Appendix A. Full constructions, proofs, and analytical details are developed in [5–7], to which we refer the reader for a deeper and more rigorous treatment. Here we only summarize the minimum pipeline needed for the present paper:

dendrogram/tree \longrightarrow Monna events \longrightarrow views distribution ρ \longrightarrow wavefunction ψ

1.2.1 Emergent Minkowski-like parameter space of relational trees

We consider a Minkowski-like parameter space for relational tree structures (finite dendrograms). Each point

$$\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4\}$$

and the resulting informational-geometric interval classifies pairs of dendrograms as time-like, space-like, or null-like separated configurations, fully analogous (in our construction) to the Minkowski classification in special relativity. Operationally, the *time-like* relation corresponds to exact induced containment of a smaller dendrogram

Fig. 1 Illustration of the relational-information framework developed recent works. An observer collects data events, and pairwise distances between events are used to perform hierarchical clustering, producing a dendrogramic tree. Each event in the tree is represented by a binary string, equivalently by its p -adic expansion. The numerical examples shown illustrate these representations and the associated 2-adic differences. The complete set of such strings/ p -adic expansions defines the relational information among all collected events and fully encodes the dendrogram structure. This relational-information set is then compressed, without loss of information, into a four-dimensional parameter space, from which the corresponding information-geometric structure emerges.

inside a larger one: there exists a subset S of leaves in T_{big} such that the contracted induced subtree satisfies

$$\text{Ind}_{T_{\text{big}}}(S) = T_{\text{small}}.$$

In this sense, an observer-history can be “growing” by adding further measurements/questions while preserving all previously established relations. In contrast, *space-like* separation corresponds to non-containment (an insertion-only inclusion distance is taken to be ∞ or 1 as stated above in Section 1.1), so no such growth map exists between the two dendrogram structures [7].

1.2.2 Emergent views-distribution parameter space

Using the Monna map, dendrogram branches are mapped to event values $event_i \in [0, 1]$. From the Monna-mapped event set, where each $event_i$ is defined from the dendrogram edge code by Eqs. (1.1)–(1.2), we define the pairwise *views*

$$q_{ik} = |event_i - event_k|, \quad k \neq i,$$

and let $Q = \{Q_j\}$ be the set of unique view-values. The associated *views distribution* is the discrete probability measure on the interval $[0, 1]$

$$\rho(Q_j) = p_j, \quad p_j = \frac{|\{q_{ik} : q_{ik} = Q_j\}|}{|\{q_{ik}\}|},$$

i.e. the normalized multiplicities of the view-values. Empirically, ρ typically exhibits a characteristic “fractal triangle” pattern, with high probability concentrated at small separations across qualitatively different dendrogram topologies. Crucially, ρ is *not* fitted: it is determined by the dendrogram’s relational structure together with its event encoding. The space of admissible views distributions admits a four-parameter coordinatization

$$\hat{\theta} = \{\hat{\theta}_1, \hat{\theta}_2, \hat{\theta}_3, \hat{\theta}_4\}, \quad \rho \equiv \rho(\hat{\theta}),$$

and equipping this $\hat{\theta}$ -space with the Rao–Fisher information metric yields a natural information-geometric manifold on which distributional dynamics may be formulated intrinsically as trajectories $\hat{\theta}(t)$ [6].

1.2.3 Views distributions as the bridge to wavefunctions

The views distribution provides a canonical route from dendrogram geometry to a complex amplitude representation. We assign an observer-dependent wavefunction whose modulus is fixed by ρ ,

$$|\psi|^2 = \rho, \quad \psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{iS},$$

where S is a phase functional (defined up to an additive constant). In the Bohmian/Hamilton–Jacobi form, S determines a momentum-like field via a (continuous or discrete) gradient,

$$p \sim \nabla S \quad (\text{or an appropriate discrete derivative on the chosen support grid}).$$

Thus, events (as defined by Eqs. (1.1)–(1.2)) \rightarrow dendrogram \rightarrow views $\rightarrow \rho$ induces a wavefunction representation

$$\text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \rho \longrightarrow \psi.$$

This one-particle representation is the starting point for the two-particle constructions introduced later in Section 2.2.

1.2.4 Non-injectivity and indistinguishability

The push-forward from dendrogram geometry to views-distribution space is generally *non-injective*, as shown in Fig. 2. Distinct dendrogram structures—either standalone L -leaf trees or embedded induced components inside a host—may correspond to different Minkowski-like parameter points $\theta \neq \theta'$, yet induce the same views distribution and therefore the same one-particle state (after fixing a phase convention):

$$\theta \neq \theta' \quad \text{but} \quad \hat{\theta}(\theta) = \hat{\theta}(\theta') \quad \iff \quad \rho(\theta) = \rho(\theta') \quad \implies \quad \psi_{\hat{\theta}(\theta)} = \psi_{\hat{\theta}(\theta')}.$$

Equivalently, the map

$$\theta \longmapsto \hat{\theta} \quad (\text{via } \rho)$$

is many-to-one: multiple distinct dendrogram realizations can collapse to a single point $\hat{\theta}$ in views-distribution space. This degeneracy is quantified in the collision statistics Fig. 3 and reappears in the exchange simulations, where different host realizations and embeddings can yield identical one- and two-particle signatures. see

1.2.5 Exchange as a mechanism for relational completion of embedded components

Since both the Minkowski-like parameter space (for dendrogram structures) and the views-distribution parameter space (for ρ) can be extended to represent not only fully relational dendrograms but also *embedded, relationally incomplete* information sets (e.g., leaf-subsets inside a larger host whose internal relations are not closed on their own), our aim is to characterize such non-relational records *relationally*. We do this by studying how embedded components behave under exchange operations in composite host contexts, and by showing that bosonic and fermionic exchanges where the Pauli-like exclusion emerges gives these non-relational sets a relational context inside a relational complete structure

In this sense, relationally incomplete embedded records become linked into a fully relational description only through their completion in a host (or host-pair) context. In this sense, relationally incomplete embedded records become linked into a fully relational description only through their completion in a host (or host-pair) context. This is conceptually (though here fully epistemic) analogous to the ontic–epistemic linkage formulated via the “objective wave function” in Appendices A.5, where an objective property acquires a wave-function representation only *relative to* an epistemic (fully relational) state on θ .

Fig. 2 Non-injectivity of the map from relational tree dynamics to views-distribution dynamics. The upper part of the figure shows distinct observer histories as worldlines in the Minkowski-like parameter space of dendrograms, labeled by different relational configurations θ . Each history determines a family of dendrogram realizations and, via the Monna-map construction, an associated set of pairwise views and a corresponding views distribution ρ . These distributions are shown schematically in the middle panel and are further represented as trajectories in the views-distribution parameter space $\hat{\theta}$ at the bottom. The figure illustrates that the push-forward $\theta \mapsto \hat{\theta}$ through ρ is generally non-injective: different dendrogram structures or worldline histories may yield identical views distributions, so that distinct points in θ -space collapse to the same effective distributional state in $\hat{\theta}$ -space. This degeneracy underlies the indistinguishability discussed in the text.

2 Results

Detached one-particle classification versus host-relative embedded realization.

Let E_1 and E_2 be two disjoint event sets of equal size n , so that

$$E_1 \cap E_2 = \emptyset, \quad |E_1| = |E_2| = n, \quad |E_1 \cup E_2| = 2n.$$

Their union defines a composite $2n$ -event record, whose realization in the Minkowski-like representation is denoted by the associated $2n$ -leaf dendrogram $T_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2)$, or equivalently by the Minkowski-like parameter point

$$\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2).$$

For each block $E \in \{E_1, E_2\}$, let

$$\theta_{\text{det}}(E) := \theta(\text{Ind}_{T_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2)}(E))$$

denote the detached Minkowski-like parameter point induced by the internal relational configuration of E ; in particular,

$$\theta_{\text{det}}(E_1), \quad \theta_{\text{det}}(E_2).$$

Applying the views map gives the corresponding detached views-distribution representatives

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_1) := \hat{\theta}(\theta_{\text{det}}(E_1)), \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_2) := \hat{\theta}(\theta_{\text{det}}(E_2)),$$

together with the detached views distributions

$$\rho_{\text{det}}(E_1), \quad \rho_{\text{det}}(E_2).$$

In the indistinguishable case, equality is imposed at the level of the reduced views representation rather than at the level of the full Minkowski-like parameter. Thus the two detached components may either remain distinct in their Minkowski-like parameters while coinciding in the reduced views description,

$$\theta_{\text{det}}(E_1) \neq \theta_{\text{det}}(E_2) \quad \text{but} \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_2),$$

or they may already coincide at the Minkowski-like level,

$$\theta_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \theta_{\text{det}}(E_2),$$

in which case their reduced views representatives also coincide. Equivalently, the two detached components belong to the same one-particle collision class whenever

$$\rho_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \rho_{\text{det}}(E_2),$$

and hence, after fixing the phase convention,

$$\psi_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \psi_{\text{det}}(E_2).$$

This defines the *detached* one-particle collision class.

However, detached collision-class data do not yet specify the contextual realization of the corresponding one-particle record. What is fixed at the detached level is only the isolated one-particle classification: distinct components may share the same detached views distribution, the same reduced representative, and hence the same detached one-particle state. The relevant distinction for the next stage of the construction is therefore between the detached representative, which describes the component out of context, and the host-relative embedded representative, which describes the realization of that same component inside a completed $2n$ -leaves host.

Single-host realization and embedded one-particle data.

Let

$$\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2)$$

denote the composite $2n$ -event host determined by the union of the two n -event blocks. Inside this host, the two blocks define two disjoint leaf sets

$$S_1 := E_1, \quad S_2 := E_2.$$

For each slot S_i , the host induces a corresponding embedded one-particle realization, whose host-relative Minkowski-like parameter is denoted by

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1), \quad \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2).$$

The associated host-relative views distributions are

$$\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1), \quad \rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2),$$

and the corresponding reduced embedded representatives are

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) := \hat{\theta}\left(\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1)\right),$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2) := \hat{\theta}\left(\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2)\right).$$

Accordingly, the associated embedded one-particle states are

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2).$$

Thus the same detached one-particle class may admit different host-relative realizations. In particular, even when

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_2),$$

so that E_1 and E_2 belong to the same detached collision class, it need not follow that

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2).$$

Indeed, the embedded realizations may satisfy either

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) = \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2)$$

or

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) \neq \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2),$$

and correspondingly either

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2)$$

or

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) \neq \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2).$$

Therefore detached equality characterizes only the isolated one-particle state obtained by detachment from context, whereas the embedded representatives describe the realization of that one-particle state within a larger relational context. It is this contextual embedded data, rather than detached collision-class membership alone, that is carried forward into the subsequent two-particle analysis. Conceptually, this mirrors the role played by detached lower-level subconfigurations in the non-ergodicity framework of relational information, where subtrees are treated out of context at one stage of the construction and acquire their physically relevant meaning only through their placement within a larger relational structure, a mechanism that in that setting underlies the emergence of CHSH-violating correlations [2, 7].

Ordered embedding and internal exchange.

Internal exchange is tested by swapping the *ordered* embedding of the two components within the same completed host. Operationally, this means reversing the order of the two measurement blocks: we either measure E_1 first and then E_2 , or measure E_2 first and then E_1 . Equivalently,

$$(E_1, E_2) \longleftrightarrow (E_2, E_1).$$

At the host level, this corresponds to reversing the ordered pair of slots

$$(S_1, S_2) \longleftrightarrow (S_2, S_1).$$

Thus internal exchange acts by

$$X_{\text{int}} : (\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1, S_2) \longleftrightarrow (\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2, S_1),$$

or, equivalently, on the embedded one-particle inputs by

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\text{int}} : & \left(\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1), \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2) \right) \\ & \longleftrightarrow \left(\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2), \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) \right). \end{aligned}$$

If the embedded representatives coincide,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2),$$

then exchange acts on two identical embedded one-particle inputs. If they remain distinct,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_1) \neq \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}(E_1 \cup E_2); S_2),$$

then exchange acts on an ordered pair of distinct host-relative embedded inputs, even though the corresponding detached components may still belong to the same detached collision class, that is, represent the same detached indistinguishable one-particle state prior to contextual embedding.

Two-host realization with four event blocks.

In the external (paired-completion) setting, the two orderings are realized not within a single completed host but across two distinct completed $2n$ -event hosts, denoted by

$$\theta_{2n}^C, \quad \theta_{2n}^D.$$

This yields four n -event blocks,

$$E_1, E_2 \subset \theta_{2n}^C, \quad E_3, E_4 \subset \theta_{2n}^D, \quad |E_i| = n,$$

with the two orderings represented as

$$(\theta_{2n}^C) : (S_1, S_2) = (E_1, E_2), \quad (\theta_{2n}^D) : (S_3, S_4) = (E_3, E_4).$$

For each slot, the corresponding host-relative embedded one-particle realization is described by its embedded Minkowski-like parameter. In the indistinguishable detached case, the four blocks are all associated with the same detached one-particle class. Thus their detached reduced representatives coincide,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_2) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_3) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_4),$$

and, after fixing the phase convention, the corresponding detached one-particle wavefunctions also coincide,

$$\psi_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \psi_{\text{det}}(E_2) = \psi_{\text{det}}(E_3) = \psi_{\text{det}}(E_4).$$

However, once these detached one-particle states are realized within the two completed hosts, their host-relative embedded realizations need not coincide. For each slot, the corresponding embedded realization is described by

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1), \quad \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2), \quad \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3), \quad \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4).$$

its reduced embedded representative,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1), \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2), \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3), \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4),$$

and the corresponding embedded one-particle states,

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4).$$

In the indistinguishable detached case, these four embedded realizations are all drawn from the same detached collision class, so that their detached one-particle representatives coincide. However, their host-relative embedded representatives need not coincide, since they depend on the particular completion and slot in which the detached one-particle state is realized.

In the external realization, exchange does not act within a single host. Rather, it swaps the *ordered pair* of embedded realizations between the two completions. Concretely, if

$$(\theta_{2n}^C) : (S_1, S_2) = (E_1, E_2), \quad (\theta_{2n}^D) : (S_3, S_4) = (E_3, E_4),$$

then external exchange acts by

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{ext}} : (S_1, S_2) \longleftrightarrow (S_4, S_3),$$

equivalently,

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{ext}} : (E_1, E_2) \longleftrightarrow (E_4, E_3).$$

At the level of embedded one-particle inputs, this means

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{ext}} : (\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1), \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2)) \longleftrightarrow (\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4), \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3)).$$

Thus external exchange reverses the order of the two contextual embedded one-particle arguments at the two-particle level, while allowing their host-relative realizations to depend on the completion in which they occur.

The exchange problem is therefore formulated not at the detached level, but at the level of the ordered pair of host-relative embedded one-particle states. Starting from the two embedded realizations

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

one forms the corresponding two-particle states by tensor product. Exchange acts by reversing the order of these two embedded inputs, namely

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) \longleftrightarrow \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1).$$

The two fundamental exchange sectors are then obtained by taking the symmetric and antisymmetric combinations of these ordered tensor-product states. In this way, bosonic and fermionic exchange behaviour are not postulated as primitive labels at the detached one-particle level; rather, they arise through the contextual composition of two embedded one-particle realizations.

Symmetric and antisymmetric two-particle compositions.

Given the ordered pair of host-relative embedded one-particle states

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

the corresponding ordered two-particle tensor-product states are

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1).$$

The two fundamental exchange sectors are obtained by taking the symmetric and antisymmetric combinations of these ordered tensor-product states:

$$\Phi^+(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) + \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \right]. \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi^-(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) - \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2) \otimes \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \right]. \quad (3)$$

By construction, Φ^+ is invariant under exchange, whereas Φ^- changes sign under exchange:

$$\chi \Phi^+ = \Phi^+, \quad \chi \Phi^- = -\Phi^-.$$

Thus the exchange problem is resolved at the level of contextual two-particle composition, not at the detached one-particle level.

Emergent spin-like interpretation.

Within the present framework, these two exchange sectors are not imposed as primitive labels of detached one-particle states. Rather, they arise only after two detached one-particle classes are realized as host-relative embedded states and then composed into a contextual two-particle system. In this sense, the symmetric sector Φ^+ defines the bosonic, spin-1-like realization, whereas the antisymmetric sector Φ^- defines the fermionic, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ -like realization. Accordingly, spin-like behaviour is not attached to the detached one-particle record as an intrinsic pre-existing property, but emerges only at the level of contextual composition and exchange.

A key consequence appears when the two host-relative embedded realizations are formed from the same detached indistinguishable one-particle class, that is, when

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{det}}(E_2), \quad \psi_{\text{det}}(E_1) = \psi_{\text{det}}(E_2).$$

Both the symmetric and antisymmetric sectors are constructed from such detached indistinguishable inputs; the difference between them arises only at the level of their contextual embedded realization. If the two embedded realizations coincide,

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) = \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

and hence

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2), \quad \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) = \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

then the antisymmetric combination vanishes identically,

$$\Phi^-(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2) = 0. \tag{4}$$

whereas the symmetric combination remains nonzero in general:

$$\Phi^+(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2) \neq 0.$$

By contrast, if the two embedded realizations remain distinct,

$$\theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \neq \theta_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

so that

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \neq \psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

then the antisymmetric state is generically nonvanishing,

$$\Phi^-(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2) \neq 0,$$

and the fermionic, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ -like sector is realized. Thus, within the present framework, the exclusion principle is not a statement about detached equality alone, but about the impossibility of sustaining a nonzero antisymmetric state when two contextual realizations of the same detached indistinguishable one-particle state collapse to the same host-relative embedded Minkowski-like state. A detached one-particle state is therefore not yet spin-labeled in itself, since in the present framework spin-like behaviour is defined only at the level of contextual two-particle composition, not at the level of the detached one-particle record alone. Only after contextual embedding and exchange do the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ -like and spin-1-like sectors become well-defined. Thus spin is not a primitive attribute of the detached one-particle state, but emerges through relational completion.

Connected versus interwoven realization.

We distinguish two geometric realization modes for the same contextual data

$$(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2),$$

applied hostwise also in the paired-completion setting. **(i) Connected (root-split).**

We say that $(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2)$ is *connected*, or *root-split*, if the root separates the leaves exactly into the two n -leaf blocks,

$$S_1 = L(\theta_{2n}^{\text{left}}), \quad S_2 = L(\theta_{2n}^{\text{right}}),$$

up to the ordering of the two root subtrees, where $\theta_{2n}^{\text{left}}$ and $\theta_{2n}^{\text{right}}$ denote the left and right root subtrees of the completed host. **(ii) Interwoven (non-root-split).** We say that $(\theta_{2n}; S_1, S_2)$ is *interwoven* if neither S_1 nor S_2 lies entirely within a single root half, i.e.

$$S_1 \cap L(\theta_{2n}^{\text{left}}) \neq \emptyset, \quad S_1 \cap L(\theta_{2n}^{\text{right}}) \neq \emptyset,$$

and similarly for S_2 .

The same detached collision-class data can therefore lead to different exchange sectors depending on how the two components are embedded in the completed host. In the connected (root-split) case, the two host-relative embedded representatives collapse to the same embedded state,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

and therefore the antisymmetric sector vanishes, so that only the symmetric, bosonic sector survives. By contrast, in the interwoven case, the two host-relative embedded representatives remain distinct,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) \neq \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

so that the antisymmetric sector is generically nonvanishing and fermionic, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ -like behaviour becomes possible. Thus the connected/interwoven distinction is the geometric mechanism by which the same detached indistinguishable input can yield bosonic-only exchange in one realization and a nontrivial fermionic sector (but also bosonic) in another.

2.1 Experimental simulation: verifying emergent bosonic/fermionic nature of dendrograms

2.1.1 From dendrogram geometry to wavefunction (and non-injectivity)

Fix the number of leaves L . Each ordered full binary dendrogram topology T is represented by a unique point $\theta(T)$ in the Minkowski-like parameter space. From $\theta(T)$ (equivalently, from the associated event set) we compute the *views distribution*

$\rho(T) = \rho$, understood here as an empirical probability distribution on the space of view-values. For a finite n -event record, its mass is supported on the finitely many *observed* view-values $Q = \{Q_j\}$, with weights given by normalized multiplicities:

$$\rho(Q_j) = p_j, \quad p_j = \frac{|\{q_{ik} : q_{ik} = Q_j\}|}{|\{q_{ik}\}|}, \quad q_{ik} = |\text{event}_i - \text{event}_k|.$$

This views distribution determines a reduced (views-distribution) parameter point $\hat{\theta}(T)$, and hence the associated wavefunction:

$$\theta(T) \longrightarrow \rho(T) \longrightarrow \hat{\theta}(T) \longrightarrow \psi_{\hat{\theta}(T)}. \quad (5)$$

The key empirical finding is that the map $T \mapsto \hat{\theta}(T)$ is generally *non-injective*: there exist distinct dendrogram topologies $T_A \neq T_B$ (equivalently, $\theta_A \neq \theta_B$) such that

$$\hat{\theta}(T_A) = \hat{\theta}(T_B), \quad \text{and therefore} \quad \psi_{\hat{\theta}(T_A)} = \psi_{\hat{\theta}(T_B)}.$$

Accordingly, for each fixed L , the set of all L -leaf dendrograms decomposes into *collision classes*: each class consists of one or more distinct topologies sharing exactly the same views distribution, and hence the same $\hat{\theta}$ and wavefunction. A class of size 1 is unique, whereas a *non-singleton* class has multiplicity at least 2.

Empirically, we observe no collisions at $L = 3$, the onset of collisions at $L = 4$, and a rapid growth in both the number of non-singleton classes and the total number of colliding topologies as L increases; see Fig. 3. This trend is consistent with the rapid growth in the number of ordered full binary trees,

$$N_L = C_{L-1},$$

governed by the Catalan numbers

$$C_n = \frac{1}{n+1} \binom{2n}{n}.$$

Finally, within the tested range $L = 3, \dots, 14$, we did not observe any cross-level collisions: no canonical views-distribution key computed at leaf count L reappeared at a different leaf count $L' \neq L$. Thus, the degeneracies reported in Fig. 3 are strictly within-level (fixed- L) phenomena.

From global collision classes to host-level exchange data.

As shown above, the map $T \mapsto \hat{\theta}(T)$ induced by the views distribution is generally non-injective: distinct L -leaf dendrograms may belong to the same *collision class*, that is, they may share the same *detached* one-particle representative $\hat{\theta}$ and hence the same detached one-particle state $\psi_{\hat{\theta}}$ after fixing the phase convention. What matters for exchange, however, is not the global (detached) classification of isolated trees, but

Fig. 3 Collision statistics for the map $T \mapsto \hat{\theta}(T)$ induced by the view distribution (pairwise $q_{ik} = |event_i - event_k|$ normalized histogram of leaf Monna map values), for $L = 3, \dots, 14$. Shown are: (i) the number of non-singleton collision classes (distinct view distributions realized by ≥ 2 topologies), (ii) the total number of topologies participating in collisions, and (iii) the maximum multiplicity of any single collision class. The y -axis is logarithmic.

the *host-level realization* of two such components as embedded subrecords inside a completed $2n$ -leaf host.

Concretely, when two colliding representatives T_A and T_B are embedded into a completed host via two disjoint slots S_1, S_2 , the one-particle inputs entering the two-particle amplitudes are the corresponding *host-relative embedded* representatives,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1), \quad \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

rather than the detached quantities $\hat{\theta}(T_A)$ and $\hat{\theta}(T_B)$. Thus, membership in the same global collision class,

$$\hat{\theta}(T_A) = \hat{\theta}(T_B),$$

does not by itself determine the exchange sector. In root-split realizations the embedded representatives may collapse to the same host-relative state, whereas in interwoven realizations they may remain distinct. This is the mechanism by which global collision structure feeds into bosonic-only exchange in one regime while still allowing nontrivial antisymmetry, and hence fermionic sectors, in another.

Numerically, the procedure therefore consists of three steps: first, identify detached collision classes through the map $T \mapsto \hat{\theta}(T)$; second, realize representatives of a given

collision class as embedded components inside completed $2n$ -leaf hosts; and third, evaluate the resulting symmetric and antisymmetric two-particle states from the corresponding host-relative embedded one-particle inputs. The simulation results below implement exactly this host-level construction.

$$(T_A, T_B) \text{ with } \hat{\theta}(T_A) = \hat{\theta}(T_B) \longrightarrow (\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1), \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2)) \longrightarrow \Phi^+, \Phi^-.$$

2.2 From host histograms to one- and two-particle states

Embedded one-particle states from host histograms.

For each completed host realization and for each occupied slot $S_i \subset L(\theta_{2n})$, we extract the corresponding embedded leaf-record, map its p -adic leaf codes to Monna-mapped event values

$$\{event_\ell\} \subset [0, 1],$$

and form the pairwise views

$$q_{\ell m} = |event_\ell - event_m|, \quad \ell \neq m.$$

Let

$$Q^{(S_i)} = \{Q_j\} \subset [0, 1]$$

denote the set of distinct observed view-values for that embedded record. The associated embedded views distribution is the empirical probability measure

$$\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)$$

supported on the finitely many observed values $Q^{(S_i)}$, with weights given by normalized multiplicities:

$$\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)(Q_j) = p_j^{(S_i)}, \quad p_j^{(S_i)} = \frac{|\{q_{\ell m} : q_{\ell m} = Q_j\}|}{|\{q_{\ell m}\}|}.$$

From this embedded views distribution we obtain the corresponding reduced embedded representative

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i) := \hat{\theta}(\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)),$$

and the associated embedded one-particle amplitude

$$\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)(Q_j) = \sqrt{\rho_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)(Q_j)} e^{iS},$$

which we normalize to

$$\tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i) = \frac{\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)}{\|\psi_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_i)\|} \in \mathbb{C}^{K_i}.$$

To assign the phase, we follow the relational prescription introduced above. First define the mean pairwise-difference quantity

$$p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \neq j} q_{jk},$$

where N is the number of admissible pairwise differences q_{jk} . We then introduce the phase S through

$$p = \partial S, \quad \partial S = e^{iS}.$$

Accordingly, the embedded one-particle amplitudes inherit a phase determined by the corresponding host-relative views data, rather than by an arbitrary global constant. Throughout the simulations, the tensor-product inputs are always these normalized *embedded* one-particle states, never the detached isolated-tree states.

Numerical two-particle exchange channels.

Given an ordered pair of embedded one-particle states, we construct the corresponding numerical two-particle channels from their tensor products. In the internal case, both orderings are realized within a single completed host θ_{2n} , and exchange acts by reversing the ordered pair of slots,

$$(S_1, S_2) \longleftrightarrow (S_2, S_1).$$

In the external (paired-completion) case, the two orderings are realized across two completed hosts,

$$\theta_{2n}^C, \quad \theta_{2n}^D,$$

with one host realizing the ordering (S_1, S_2) and the other the reversed ordering. From these ordered realizations we define the two canonical channel families

$$\Phi_1^\pm = \frac{1}{2} \left(\tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1) \otimes \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2) \pm \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4) \otimes \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3) \right), \quad (6)$$

$$\Phi_2^\pm = \frac{1}{2} \left(\tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_1) \otimes \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^C; S_2) \pm \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_3) \otimes \tilde{\psi}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}^D; S_4) \right). \quad (7)$$

In the internal case $\theta_{2n}^C = \theta_{2n}^D$, these reduce to the usual within-host combinations of the two orderings of the same embedded pair. In the external case $\theta_{2n}^C \neq \theta_{2n}^D$, they combine the two orderings across two completed hosts.

Symmetry-weight diagnostics under particle exchange.

Let P denote particle exchange (swap of tensor factors), defined on simple tensors by

$$P(u \otimes v) = v \otimes u,$$

and extended linearly to the full tensor-product space. For any channel

$$\Phi \in \{\Phi_1^+, \Phi_1^-, \Phi_2^+, \Phi_2^-\},$$

we form its symmetric and antisymmetric parts,

$$\Phi^{(\text{sym})} = \frac{1}{2}(\Phi + P\Phi), \quad \Phi^{(\text{anti})} = \frac{1}{2}(\Phi - P\Phi),$$

and define the corresponding weights

$$w_{\text{sym}} = \|\Phi^{(\text{sym})}\|^2, \quad w_{\text{anti}} = \|\Phi^{(\text{anti})}\|^2,$$

together with the normalized weights

$$\hat{w}_{\text{sym}} = \frac{w_{\text{sym}}}{\|\Phi\|^2}, \quad \hat{w}_{\text{anti}} = \frac{w_{\text{anti}}}{\|\Phi\|^2}.$$

We classify a channel as *bosonic by weight* if

$$|\hat{w}_{\text{sym}} - 1| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{strict}},$$

as *fermionic by weight* if

$$|\hat{w}_{\text{anti}} - 1| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{strict}},$$

and otherwise as *mixed*.

Exchange eigenphase diagnostics.

Independently of the symmetry weights, we test whether Φ is an approximate eigenstate of particle exchange:

$$P\Phi \approx \lambda \Phi.$$

Whenever a stable eigenvalue λ is obtained, we normalize it to unit modulus,

$$\lambda_N = \frac{\lambda}{|\lambda|} = e^{i\vartheta},$$

and record the exchange eigenphase $\vartheta \in (-\pi, \pi]$. With tolerance δ_ϕ , we classify the channel as bosonic by phase if

$$|\vartheta| \leq \delta_\phi,$$

fermionic by phase if ϑ lies within δ_ϕ of $\pm\pi$, anyonic if a stable phase exists away from 0 and $\pm\pi$, and undefined if no stable eigenrelation is obtained.

Recorded observables and enumeration of realizations.

For each detached collision-class input, each admissible host realization (internal or external), and each channel

$$\Phi \in \{\Phi_1^+, \Phi_1^-, \Phi_2^+, \Phi_2^-\},$$

we record: the norm $\|\Phi\|^2$, the symmetry weights $w_{\text{sym}}, w_{\text{anti}}$, the normalized weights $\hat{w}_{\text{sym}}, \hat{w}_{\text{anti}}$, the corresponding weight-based label, and, whenever defined, the exchange

eigenphase ϑ together with its phase-based label. All subsequent bosonic/fermionic counts refer to these two-particle diagnostics.

In the interwoven regime, many completed hosts admit two disjoint embedded records realizing the two orderings either internally on a single host or externally across a host pair. The same construction is applied to all eligible realizations. For computational efficiency, the norms and exchange diagnostics are evaluated from one-particle inner products whenever possible, without explicitly materializing the full tensor-product vectors.

2.2.1 Connected (root-split) exchange statistics

We quantify exchange behavior in the *connected* (root-split) regime for $L = 3, 4, 5$. Each realization is assigned to one of the four channels Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm and evaluated by two complementary diagnostics: (i) a *strict* criterion based on pure symmetric/antisymmetric exchange weight, and (ii) a *phase-sector* criterion based on whether the state behaves as an eigenstate of the particle-exchange operator with eigenphase near 0 (bosonic) or π (fermionic). Figure 4 summarizes both diagnostics (top: strict, bottom: phase-sector).

Single-host versus two-host identification (physical de-duplication).

In the connected/root-split setting, the same physical configuration may be recorded in two orientations corresponding to the two orderings of the embedded pair. For the physical interpretation, we therefore distinguish realizations in which the two embedded components arise from the *same* detached dendrogram from those in which they arise from *distinct* detached dendrograms with the same views distribution:

$$T_A = T_B \Rightarrow \text{single-host (internal) contribution}, \quad T_A \neq T_B \Rightarrow \text{two-host (external) contribution.}$$

Accordingly, Fig. 4 separates the $T_A = T_B$ and $T_A \neq T_B$ contributions.

Empirical outcome: no connected fermionic events for $L = 3, 4, 5$.

After physical-host de-duplication, we observe *zero* connected fermionic events for all $L \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ and for all four channels:

$$\forall L \in \{3, 4, 5\}, \forall \Phi \in \{\Phi_1^\pm, \Phi_2^\pm\} : \quad N_{\text{ferm}}(L, \Phi) = 0.$$

Thus, throughout the connected/root-split regime covered by our analysis, antisymmetric exchange is not realized. In the connected realizations observed here, the two root-halves induce the same embedded views representative,

$$\hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_1) = \hat{\theta}_{\text{emb}}(\theta_{2n}; S_2),$$

and hence the same normalized embedded one-particle state (up to the assigned phase), so the two-particle construction collapses to the exchange-symmetric sector.

Bosonic support: strict versus phase-sector diagnostics.

All connected realizations in these datasets are therefore classified as bosonic under the strict and/or phase-sector diagnostics, with a clear decomposition into same-host and two-host contributions.

Strict diagnostic. Only the + channels are populated:

$$\begin{aligned} L = 3 : & \quad \Phi_1^+ : (2, 0), & \quad \Phi_2^+ : (2, 0), \\ L = 4 : & \quad \Phi_1^+ : (5, 3), & \quad \Phi_2^+ : (5, 3), \\ L = 5 : & \quad \Phi_1^+ : (14, 9), & \quad \Phi_2^+ : (14, 9), \end{aligned}$$

while Φ_1^- and Φ_2^- remain empty throughout.

Phase-sector diagnostic. The phase-sector criterion is less selective and classifies all four channels as bosonic once $L \geq 3$, with the same single-host/two-host split:

$$\begin{aligned} L = 3 : & \quad \Phi_1^\pm, \Phi_2^\pm : (2, 0) \text{ in each channel,} \\ L = 4 : & \quad \Phi_1^\pm, \Phi_2^\pm : (5, 3) \text{ in each channel,} \\ L = 5 : & \quad \Phi_1^\pm, \Phi_2^\pm : (14, 9) \text{ in each channel.} \end{aligned}$$

This strict-versus-phase comparison is expected: the strict criterion requires purity of the symmetric/antisymmetric weights and is therefore more selective, whereas the phase criterion labels any approximate exchange eigenstate with eigenphase near 0 as bosonic.

Experimental consequences in the connected/root-split regime.

The connected results admit a sharp interpretation in the Minkowski-like parameter space of relational trees.

1. **Self-composition is bosonic.** Whenever the embedded components coincide ($T_A = T_B$, and hence $\theta_{n_1} = \theta_{n_2}$ in Minkowski-like space), the observed exchange response in the $2n$ -leaf root-connected host is exclusively bosonic. In this sense, each dendrogram state behaves bosonically under root-connected composition with itself: the composite configuration supports only the exchange-symmetric sector.
2. **Collision classes in views space remain bosonic under connected composition.** A more informative case is when two *distinct* dendrograms correspond to distinct Minkowski-like points,

$$\theta_1 \neq \theta_2,$$

but collapse to the same views-distribution point,

$$\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2,$$

and hence, after the phase prescription is fixed, to the same detached one-particle state. In the connected/root-split regime, such pairs still generate *only bosonic* exchange signatures. Under the strict diagnostic, the bosonic population appears only in the + channels; under the phase-sector diagnostic, bosonic behavior extends across all four channels. Thus, within root-connected composition, views-space indistinguishability is realized as exchange symmetry rather than antisymmetry.

3. **Bosonic exchange relates distinct hosts in the $T_A \neq T_B$ sector.** When $T_A \neq T_B$, exchanging the two root-halves maps one host configuration to a generally different host configuration,

$$\theta_{2n} \mapsto \theta'_{2n} \neq \theta_{2n}.$$

These two hosts are distinct Minkowski-like points and, by the definition adopted above, are naturally interpreted as *space-like separated* realizations of the composite system. Nevertheless, the connected data show that the exchange relation between these two hosts remains purely bosonic: the swap connects θ_{2n} and θ'_{2n} through exchange-symmetric two-particle structure, and no fermionic channel is realized. Thus, even when the composite system is represented by two different space-like host points, the exchange relation between them remains bosonic.

Across all connected/root-split configurations tested at $L = 3, 4, 5$, antisymmetric exchange is absent. Both the self sector ($T_A = T_B$) and the distinct sector ($T_A \neq T_B$) realize only bosonic exchange structure, with the strict diagnostic selecting a sparse subset of + channels and the phase-sector diagnostic revealing a broader bosonic support.

2.2.2 Interwoven exchange statistics

We next analyze the *interwoven* regime. Unlike the connected (root-split) case, interwoven embeddings admit a large multiplicity of admissible host realizations, and this is precisely the regime in which fermionic cases are expected to emerge.

Host-coincidence indicator $C=D$.

In the interwoven regime, C and D label the host realization(s) on which the two-particle construction is evaluated. We write

$$\theta_{2n}^C, \quad \theta_{2n}^D$$

for the two completed $2n$ -leaf host realizations carrying the two ordered embeddings of the same (T_A, T_B) input. There are then two possibilities:

$$\theta_{2n}^C = \theta_{2n}^D \iff \text{single-host case (internal realization),}$$

$$\theta_{2n}^C \neq \theta_{2n}^D \iff \text{two-host case (external realization).}$$

In the single-host case, C/D functions only as an orientation tag for two ordered embeddings inside the same host. In the two-host case, it labels two distinct completed hosts related by the swap operation. Accordingly, we use the binary indicator $C=D$ versus $C \neq D$ to distinguish internal exchange events supported on a single completed host from external exchange events supported on two distinct completed hosts.

Two binary splits: tree coincidence and host coincidence.

Each interwoven event is classified by two independent binary relations: (i) whether the embedded trees coincide ($T_A=T_B$ versus $T_A \neq T_B$), and (ii) whether the hosts

Fig. 4 Connected (root-split) exchange statistics for $L = 3, 4, 5$. *Top: strict diagnostic (phi_weight_kind); bottom: phase-sector diagnostic (phi_phase_kind)*. In each panel, bosonic/bosonic events are split into **same physical host** ($T_A=T_B$, blue) versus **two hosts** ($T_A \neq T_B$, orange) using the exchange-identification rule $ab \sim ba$ when $T_A = T_B$ (with physical-host de-duplication). No fermionic/fermionic events are observed in these connected logs for $L = 3, 4, 5$ under either diagnostic. Dashed vertical lines separate the leaf-count blocks.

coincide ($C=D$ versus $C \neq D$). We report all counts in the resulting four-way partition

$$(T_A=T_B, C=D), \quad (T_A=T_B, C \neq D), \quad (T_A \neq T_B, C=D), \quad (T_A \neq T_B, C \neq D),$$

and we do so separately for the two diagnostics: *strict* and *phase-sector*.

Bosonic support: strict versus phase-sector diagnostics.

As shown in Fig. 5 (top two panels), the bosonic counts under the strict diagnostic are comparatively sparse and highly channel-selective: the dominant mass sits in Φ_1^+ ,

with a much smaller contribution in Φ_2^+ , while Φ_1^- and Φ_2^- are nearly absent across $L = 3, 4, 5$.

At $L = 3$, strict bosonic events occur only in the $T_A=T_B$ sector; no strict-boson counts with $T_A \neq T_B$ appear in any channel since there isn't any pair of same detached wave function for $T_A \neq T_B$. For $L \geq 4$, substantial strict-boson counts appear in the mixed sectors involving $T_A \neq T_B$, especially in Φ_1^+ . For example, at $L = 5$ in Φ_1^+ we observe 1800 events in the $(T_A \neq T_B, C=D)$ sector and 37 events in $(T_A \neq T_B, C \neq D)$.

The phase-sector diagnostic is markedly less selective and yields very large bosonic counts across all four channels Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm , with rapid growth in L and strong support in both host-relations $C=D$ and $C \neq D$. In particular, once $L \geq 4$, all four $(T_A=T_B) \times (C=D)$ sectors contribute in all channels, and the largest counts typically occur in the $C \neq D$ sectors, reflecting the abundance of distinct host pairs in the interwoven search.

Fermionic support appears only in the minus channels.

The bottom two panels of Fig. 5 show the fermionic counts. A striking and robust feature is that fermionic events appear *only* in the minus channels: Φ_1^- carries the overwhelming majority of the fermionic mass, while Φ_2^- is present but much smaller. No fermionic events are observed in Φ_1^+ or Φ_2^+ for $L = 3, 4, 5$ under either diagnostic.

At the level of magnitudes, the fermionic signal is dominated by the $T_A=T_B$ sectors, and especially by the coincident-host sector $(T_A=T_B, C=D)$. For Φ_1^- , this sector grows from 42 events at $L = 3$ to 428 at $L = 4$ and 4286 at $L = 5$. A substantial secondary contribution arises from $(T_A \neq T_B, C=D)$ in Φ_1^- (for example, 151 at $L = 4$ and 1793 at $L = 5$), while $C \neq D$ fermionic counts remain comparatively small in both Φ_1^- and Φ_2^- .

Strict versus phase agreement for fermions.

For fermionic events, the strict and phase-sector panels coincide numerically on $L = 3, 4, 5$, with the same counts in each channel and sector. This indicates that whenever a fermionic phase-eigen relation is detected in these interwoven data, the symmetric/antisymmetric weights are already essentially pure at the strict tolerance. This contrasts with the bosonic case, where the phase-sector diagnostic admits many more events than the strict weight-purity criterion.

Interpretation of the interwoven data.

A key conceptual difference in the interwoven regime is that the two embedded components should not be interpreted as autonomous n -leaf objects carrying a closed relational meaning by themselves. Because the leaf sets are distributed across the host, each induced embedded record is best regarded as a relationally incomplete subrecord whose closure is supplied only at the level of the completed host. Thus, the bosonic/fermionic label extracted from Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm is not a property of the isolated embedded component taken alone, but of the relationally completed configuration defined by the host (when $C=D$) or by the host pair (when $C \neq D$).

From this viewpoint, the large bosonic population is the generic signature of *symmetric* relational completion across many admissible hosts, whereas the fermionic

population is a structured, channel-restricted *antisymmetric* completion mode that becomes available precisely because the embedded components are not separately relationally closed. This explains simultaneously why bosonic exchange becomes far more abundant and less channel-restricted than in the connected/root-split regime, and why fermionic exchange can appear here even though it is absent in the connected logs: antisymmetry is realized at the level of host completion, whether within a single completed host or across two distinct space-like hosts. In this sense, exchange acts as a *relationalization map*: it takes two embedded, relationally incomplete records inside a $2n$ -leaf system and produces a well-defined relational statement by comparing them under swap in the completed host geometry.

2.2.3 Non-disjoint exchange statistics and time-like host embedding

The interwoven analysis above imposed disjointness of the two embedded records; we now relax that requirement. In the *non-disjoint two-host* analysis, the two realizations associated with (T_A, T_B) are no longer required to be supported on disjoint leaf subsets of a host. The supporting leaf sets may overlap, and one realization may be nested inside the other. We analyze the aggregated two-host event tables for $L \in \{3, 4, 5\}$. Each recorded event is assigned to one of the four exchange channels Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm and evaluated by two complementary diagnostics: a *strict* (weight-purity) criterion and a *phase-sector* (exchange-eigenphase) criterion. Figure 6 summarizes the resulting bosonic and fermionic event counts (log scale) across channels and leaf numbers.

Host relations as causal structure.

Each event involves two completed host realizations,

$$\theta_{2n}^C, \quad \theta_{2n}^D.$$

We stratify events by the relation between these two host geometries into three cases: (i) **identical** hosts, $\theta_{2n}^C = \theta_{2n}^D$; (ii) **embedded** hosts, where one host embeds in the other; and (iii) **not-embedded** hosts, where neither embedding direction holds. In the Minkowski-like parameter space of relational trees, this stratification has a direct interpretation: embedded host pairs correspond to **time-like** separation, because one host is realized as a nested substructure of the other and therefore carries an intrinsic containment order, whereas not-embedded pairs are naturally interpreted as **space-like**, since neither host contains the other.

Main empirical outcome: fermionic exchange persists in time-like and space-like sectors.

Unlike the connected/root-split regime (Sec. 2.2.1), the non-disjoint two-host analysis produces a substantial fermionic population. Crucially, fermionic events are not confined to identical-host realizations: they remain present both when the two hosts are **embedded** (time-like) and when they are **not embedded** (space-like). Thus antisymmetric exchange signatures survive under genuine changes of host geometry, including nested (causal) host evolution.

Fig. 5 Interwoven exchange statistics for $L = 3, 4, 5$ (log scale), split by $(T_A=T_B) \times (C=D)$. Four-panel summary of interwoven events from `phi_ab_events_L3.csv`, `..._L4.csv`, `..._L5.csv`. Within each panel, bars are partitioned into the four sectors $(T_A=T_B, C=D)$, $(T_A=T_B, C \neq D)$, $(T_A \neq T_B, C=D)$, and $(T_A \neq T_B, C \neq D)$, where host-coincidence $C=D$ is determined by comparing normalized host labels after stripping the leading C_{\cdot}/D_{\cdot} prefix. *Top*: strict bosons (`phi_weight_kind=boson`). *Second*: phase-sector bosons (`phi_phase_kind=bosonic`). *Third*: strict fermions (`phi_weight_kind=fermion`). *Bottom*: phase-sector fermions (`phi_phase_kind=fermionic`). Fermionic support is confined to the minus channels Φ_1^- and Φ_2^- , with Φ_1^- dominant, whereas bosonic counts are broadly distributed under the phase-sector diagnostic and comparatively sparse under the strict diagnostic. Dashed vertical lines separate the leaf-count blocks.

Strict versus phase-sector diagnostics.

The strict and phase-sector diagnostics agree at the level of qualitative structure: both reveal robust bosonic and fermionic channels once overlap is permitted. Quantitatively, the strict criterion is more selective, since it requires near-pure symmetric or antisymmetric weight, whereas the phase-sector criterion detects approximate exchange eigenstates even when the weights are not strictly pure. Accordingly, phase-sector counts are typically larger, but the dependence on host relation (identical, embedded/time-like, or not-embedded/space-like) is consistent across the two diagnostics.

Scaling with L and channel structure.

As L increases, the recorded bosonic and fermionic counts increase sharply, see Fig. 6. The largest counts occur at $L = 5$. The distribution across the four channels Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm varies with L , and the split among identical, embedded, and not-embedded host pairs also depends on channel. The only consistent feature across all tested leaf numbers is that *embedded* (time-like) host pairs appear in every channel; they never disappear. In particular, fermionic events are present not only for identical hosts, but also for embedded and not-embedded host pairs.

3 Discussion

A central conclusion of the present work is that bosonic versus fermionic behaviour is not an intrinsic label of the detached one-particle state. Rather, it is a property of the *contextual two-particle realization*: the exchange sector is determined only after detached one-particle inputs are realized as host-relative embedded states and then compared under exchange. In this sense, the same detached collision-class input can support distinct effective exchange sectors depending on the completed host realization, the embedding pattern, and whether the comparison is internal (single-host) or external (two-host).

This conclusion is visible already in the disjoint $2L$ -host construction. Any non-identical host pair

$$(\theta_{2L}^C, \theta_{2L}^D)$$

in that setting is *space-like separated* in the Minkowski-like parameter space: both hosts have exactly $2L$ leaves, so neither can occur as an induced (contracted) subtree of the other, and therefore no time-like containment relation is possible. The same space-like behaviour appears more generally in the $L+1$ -to- $2L-1$ regimes whenever two dendrograms cannot be embedded into one another. In that regime, the relevant relation probed by our analysis is the exchange signature itself, namely the relative organization of the two embedded L -leaf structures (T_A, T_B) across θ_{2L}^C and θ_{2L}^D , rather than any causal nesting relation between the hosts.

Within this setting, “fermionic” is not a label of T_A or T_B taken separately. It is a property of the *two-particle realization*, i.e. of how two embedded copies are placed inside one or two completed hosts and how those host-relative realizations are compared under exchange. Concretely, fermionic events are associated with cases in which the two embedded leaf-records fail to close into a single admissible relational

Fig. 6 Non-disjoint exchange statistics for $L = 3, 4, 5$, stratified by host relation (log scale). Events are grouped by Φ -channel (Φ_1^\pm, Φ_2^\pm) and split by the relation between the two completed hosts ($\theta_{2n}^C, \theta_{2n}^D$): **identical**, **embedded**, and **not embedded**. The left column shows bosonic counts and the right column shows fermionic counts; the top row uses the strict weight diagnostic, and the bottom row uses the phase-sector diagnostic. Bar heights are plotted on a logarithmic y -axis, with values annotated above bars. Vertical dashed lines separate the L blocks. In the Minkowski-like containment metric on relational trees, the **embedded** stratum corresponds to a **time-like** host-containment relation, while **not embedded** corresponds to a **space-like** non-containment relation. Both bosonic and fermionic events occur in each stratum, with rapidly increasing counts at larger L .

object under the relevant host completion, whereas bosonic events are associated with realizations in which relational closure is preserved, most transparently in the connected/root-split geometry where the two components occur as the two root-children of a host. More generally, the same pair (T_A, T_B) can produce bosonic or fermionic outcomes depending only on the host choice and on the embedding pattern, including whether

$$\theta_{2n}^C = \theta_{2n}^D \quad \text{or} \quad \theta_{2n}^C \neq \theta_{2n}^D.$$

A central empirical message of our simulations is therefore *context dependence*. The same pair (T_A, T_B) can exhibit bosonic or fermionic exchange behaviour under different completed host realizations

$$(\theta_{2n}^C, \theta_{2n}^D)$$

and different placements inside them. Operationally, the bosonic/fermionic label is attached to the *two-particle construction* built from the *embedded* one-particle states extracted from the host(s). In the internal case

$$\theta_{2n}^C = \theta_{2n}^D,$$

the two orderings of the embeddings are realized inside one host and exchange swaps the ordering of the embedded pair. In the external case

$$\theta_{2n}^C \neq \theta_{2n}^D,$$

the two orderings are realized on two different hosts. The channels Φ_1^\pm and Φ_2^\pm are simply the \pm combinations of these ordered realizations, and the exchange test is applied only after forming the corresponding Φ . Thus exchange statistics are a property of the *embedding pattern and host context* that couple two realizations, not a property of T_A , T_B , or a single host taken in isolation.

This point can be stated sharply in the language of our two parameter spaces. The map

$$\theta \longrightarrow \hat{\theta} \longrightarrow \psi_{\hat{\theta}}$$

is many-to-one at the first step: distinct Minkowski-like points θ can induce the same distribution coordinate $\hat{\theta}$, and hence the same one-particle wavefunction. The exclusion-like constraint is therefore not enforced by locality in θ -space itself, but by the fact that distinct θ -realizations may correspond to the *same* one-particle state $\psi_{\hat{\theta}}$. When such indistinguishable constituents are placed into a composite host context, the remaining structure capable of distinguishing the exchange sector is the *embedding relation*; it is precisely there that antisymmetric (fermionic) versus symmetric (bosonic) channels emerge [18]. In this sense, exclusion is not a primitive rule on detached one-particle states, but an emergent consequence of contextual two-particle completion.

A broader conceptual point is that the present results fit a pattern already visible in our earlier work on non-ergodicity and CHSH violation [2, 7]. There, detached relational representations θ , when linked contextually and non-ergodically inside a larger

informational setting, gave rise to quantum-like entanglement phenomena and Bell-type violations. In the present work, we find an analogous mechanism at the level of exchange: detached indistinguishable one-particle units do not yet carry bosonic or fermionic meaning by themselves, but acquire exclusion-like behaviour, exchange symmetry, and antisymmetry only through their host-relative embedding inside a larger relational completion. In both cases, the quantum-like effect is not attached to the detached unit taken in isolation; it emerges from the relation between the detached unit and the larger context in which it is completed.

This extends a theme that already appeared in the objective-wave-function construction of Appendix A.5 and in [7], where an objective informational content, effectively non-relational when taken in isolation, acquired a wave-function representation only relative to an epistemic relational state. From this viewpoint, the theory is revealing a second form of correspondence between non-relational and relational informational structures. The detached units entering the present construction are, in themselves, fully relationally complete objects. However, once embedded into a larger host, each may behave effectively as non-relational when considered separately at the level relevant for exchange, whereas together they define a composite structure with Minkowski-like relational character. Thus, well-defined quantum-like behaviour emerges not from either detached unit alone, but from their joint contextual realization inside the host. For this reason, the possibility of extending the Minkowski-like framework beyond fully relational dendrograms to more general informational sets, whether relational or effectively non-relational-in the sense of appearing absolute when taken in isolation deserves further study.

The fermionic cases we observe, predominantly in the minus channels Φ_1^- and Φ_2^- , admit a natural analogy with the two-electron spin singlet: a state may be antisymmetric under exchange even though any *single-particle summary* appears exchange-symmetric. In the present framework, host-level histograms or embedded one-particle views distributions do not by themselves encode an exchange sign; the sign is determined only after forming the two-particle channel Φ and testing it under the swap operator P . Thus the exchange sign is not a property of T_A or T_B alone, but of the joint two-particle construction induced by the embedding context. This is also why a detached one-particle state is not yet spin-labeled in itself: spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ -like and spin-1-like behaviour become well-defined only at the level of contextual two-particle composition.

In this respect, our results are broadly consonant with the spirit of Rovelli's relational quantum mechanics, in which physical properties are not treated as absolute intrinsic attributes of isolated systems, but become meaningful only in relational contexts[39]. Here, spin-like exchange behaviour is likewise not attached to the detached one-particle record taken in isolation, but becomes well-defined only through host-dependent embedding and exchange of dendrographic records.

Taken together, these results indicate a form of *boson-fermion transmutation by relational reorganization*: changing the host pair and/or the embedding pattern can map an effectively bosonic composite description into an effectively fermionic one, and conversely, without changing the underlying detached one-particle state $\psi_{\hat{\rho}}$. The analogy to supersymmetry [40] is therefore structural rather than literal.

What is transformed is not a particle species, and no partner spectrum is introduced. Rather, an operation on relational organization, implemented by host and embedding rearrangement, acts as a transformation between effective exchange sectors.

More generally, our numerical procedure also logs *mixed* and *anyonic* cases, although we do not analyze them systematically here. By “mixed” we mean two-particle channels that are neither purely bosonic nor purely fermionic under the symmetry-weight decomposition, while “anyonic” refers to channels with a stable non-trivial exchange eigenphase, distinct from the bosonic (0) and fermionic (π) cases. Their appearance suggests that different host realizations and embedding patterns of the same pair (T_A, T_B) may generate a broader spectrum of exchange behaviour, ranging from bosonic through mixed or phase-nontrivial regimes to fermionic. Understanding how this spectrum is organized by host geometry and relational embedding is left for future work.

Finally, our findings motivate a broader interpretation of “matter” as an emergent signature of *broken relational closure*. A fully relational configuration is one whose information can be consistently recomposed into a single admissible composite dendrogram: the parts are not independent objects, but only mutually defining relations. When such a configuration is partitioned into subsets whose p -adic leaf expansions are no longer jointly composable, so that no admissible dendrogram can reconstitute them as one relational whole, the resulting pieces behave as *non-relational residues*. These residues support particle-like degrees of freedom whose exchange character is determined not by intrinsic identity, but by how the residues are embedded and compared inside larger relational contexts. In this sense, matter is not added on top of relations; it is the stable operational footprint of a relational structure precisely when its capacity for relational recomposition has been disrupted.

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A Short overview of recent results

A.1 Emergent Minkowski-like parameter space of relational trees

We briefly recall the construction developed in our previous studies [5–7], where two complementary parameter spaces were introduced: (i) a parameter space for dendrograms themselves, viewed as relational tree structures, and (ii) a parameter space for the views distributions induced by those trees. We begin with the Minkowski-like parameter space for dendrograms. Each point

$$\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4\}$$

represents a unique dendrographic relational structure at a fixed event-level (number of leaves/measurements). This space is not merely a coordinate representation: it is endowed with a causal organization induced by the possible *growth* of relational structures as observers acquire additional measurements.

Ensemble-of-observers construction and dendrographic worldlines.

Consider an ensemble of observers, in the idealized limit $N \rightarrow \infty$. An observer who has collected m events

$$e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m$$

constructs a dendrogram encoding the relations among those events. Upon measuring a new event e_{m+1} , the observer updates the dendrogram to the next level. At each event-level m , the ensemble distributes over the set of admissible dendrogram structures; a given dendrogram D at level m is realized by some nonzero fraction of observers, say $n(D)/N > 0$. A *single observer* therefore traces a sequence of dendrograms across levels, which we interpret as a *worldline* through the dendrogram parameter space:

$$D^{(m)} \longrightarrow D^{(m+1)} \longrightarrow D^{(m+2)} \longrightarrow \dots \quad \iff \quad \theta^{(m)} \longrightarrow \theta^{(m+1)} \longrightarrow \theta^{(m+2)} \longrightarrow \dots$$

Here each $\theta^{(m)}$ encodes the observer’s relational state at level m . Since observers may acquire any admissible new event at each step, the causal structure is formulated statistically at the ensemble level rather than as a deterministic path rule for a single observer.

Non-uniqueness of event sets and equality of dendrograms.

Different observers may collect different sets of events and nevertheless obtain the *same* dendrographic relational structure. For two level- m event sets set_1 and set_2 with associated dendrograms D_1 and D_2 , one may have: (i) $\text{set}_1 = \text{set}_2$, trivially implying $D_1 = D_2$; (ii) $\text{set}_1 \cap \text{set}_2 = \emptyset$, yet the relational structure still coincides, so that $D_1 = D_2$; or partial overlap, where the induced relations may or may not agree. Thus a point θ should be understood as an *equivalence class of measurement histories* that share the same relational configuration.

Causal separation: timelike versus spacelike dendrograms.

The key structural question is whether a dendrogram D_1 at event-level e_1 can evolve to another dendrogram D_2 at level $e_2 \geq e_1$ after the acquisition of $e_2 - e_1$ additional events. This leads to the causal definitions:

- **Timelike separation.** D_1 and D_2 are timelike separated if and only if at least one observer with dendrogram D_1 at level e_1 can evolve to D_2 after acquiring the next $e_2 - e_1$ events.
- **Spacelike separation.** D_1 and D_2 are spacelike separated if and only if no observer with dendrogram D_1 at level e_1 evolves to D_2 after acquiring the next $e_2 - e_1$ events.

In particular, all distinct dendrograms at the same level are spacelike separated in this sense.

Containment interpretation (induced-subtree criterion).

This causal distinction admits a clean structural formulation. Timelike separation corresponds to exact induced containment of a smaller dendrogram inside a larger one: there exists a subset S of leaves in a larger dendrogram T_{big} such that the contracted induced subtree

$$\text{Ind}_{T_{\text{big}}}(S)$$

is exactly a given smaller dendrogram T_{small} . Thus timelike separated dendrograms are precisely those for which the smaller relational structure is contained, as an induced restriction, in the larger one. Operationally, this means that a dendrogram can evolve to a larger one by adding more measurements while preserving the previously established relational content.

By contrast, spacelike separation corresponds to non-containment: the required induced restriction cannot be realized. Equivalently, an insertion-only inclusion distance is effectively infinite. In that case, a dendrogram cannot be transformed into the larger one by any growth process that preserves the demanded induced relations.

Light cones in dendrogram space.

For a unique dendrogram D , equivalently a point θ , its *future light cone* consists of all dendrograms that can evolve from D under admissible event extensions, while its *past light cone* consists of all dendrograms that could have evolved into D . This yields a dendrographic analogue of Minkowski causal structure: points in the future or past cone are timelike related to θ , while points outside these cones are spacelike related. In this sense, the parameter space is Minkowski-like not merely by coordinate count, but by the induced causal organization coming from ensemble-observer flow.

Epistemic–ontic linkage.

A finite dendrogram at level m is an *epistemic* relational state, shared by a nonzero fraction of observers. In the limit of indefinitely many acquired events, each observer approaches a unique infinite dendrogram, interpreted as an *ontic* object corresponding to a unique infinite worldline through the parameter space. Conversely, a finite point θ may be regarded as encoding a set of compatible ontic infinite dendrograms

or worldlines. Intersections of such sets correspond to timelike relatedness between epistemic points; empty intersections correspond to spacelike separation.

Lossless real parametrization of dendrograms.

A central analytical result of the earlier construction is that the relational information carried by dendrogram branches, viewed as p -adic strings (with $p = 2$ in the present applications), can be compressed without loss into a finite real parametrization. Concretely, branches are represented by 2-adic expansions, mapped to rational event-values in $[0, 1]$ via the Monna map, and combined into real-valued summary functionals. From these one constructs the four-parameter coordinate point

$$\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4\},$$

with the defining property that equality of the four coordinates implies equality of the underlying dendrogram structure. This provides the bridge from discrete relational trees to a continuous four-dimensional coordinate representation.

Informational Minkowski metric and continuum embedding.

Once this four-parameter encoding is available, one can define an informational distance between dendrogram points that depends on both (i) their ensemble observer-flow structure, through past/future light-cone relations, and (ii) their level separation. Analytically, this distance acquires the required sign structure: it is negative for timelike-related dendrograms and positive for spacelike-related dendrograms, thereby reproducing a Minkowski-like interval classification on the dendrogram parameter space.

The same construction also supports a smooth continuum description. Each dendrogram may be associated with a distribution on an auxiliary (t, x, y, z) space whose Fisher information metric yields, after rescaling, a Minkowski-signature matrix. A simultaneity-like operator depending on level difference then modifies the interval so that the resulting quadratic form behaves as a Minkowski-like distance between dendrogram states. In this way, the discrete dendrogram space may be treated as embedded in a smooth four-dimensional manifold, allowing the use of differential-geometric tools even though the underlying objects arise from finite relational trees.

Remark on relational completeness.

Although the Minkowski-like space is constructed to parameterize *relationally complete* dendrogram structures, the same encoding may also represent certain sets of information strings, for example partial p -adic records, that do not themselves form a closed relational dendrogram. This flexibility becomes important later, when embedded or induced components inside larger hosts may be relationally incomplete, while the composite host restores relational completeness.

A.2 Emergent views-distribution parameter space

From dendrogram edges to a probability measure on relational separations.

Given an n -leaf dendrogram, each leaf-edge (root-to-leaf branch) admits a finite 2-adic expansion

$$\text{edge}_i = \sum_{j=0}^k a_j 2^j, \quad a_j \in \{0, 1\}.$$

Applying the Monna map sends this discrete relational code to a real event coordinate in $[0, 1]$,

$$\text{event}_i = \sum_{j=0}^k a_j 2^{-j-1} \in [0, 1].$$

In this way, the dendrogram is represented by a finite set of rational points on $[0, 1]$ that still encode the same hierarchy. We then define the pairwise *views*, i.e. relational separation magnitudes,

$$q_{ik} = |\text{event}_i - \text{event}_k|, \quad i \neq k,$$

and collect the set of distinct observed view-values $Q = \{Q_j\}$. The *views distribution* ρ is the empirical probability mass function on Q ,

$$\rho(Q_j) = p_j, \quad p_j = \frac{|\{q_{ik} : q_{ik} = Q_j\}|}{|\{q_{ik}\}|}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Thus each dendrogram canonically induces a probability distribution over relational separation scales.

Typical geometry and continuum limit.

Across qualitatively different dendrogram constructions, ρ exhibits a robust “fractal-triangle” shape with enhanced weight near small view-values. This reflects the fact that the pipeline

$$\text{data} \longrightarrow \text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \{\text{event}_i\} \longrightarrow \{q_{ik}\} \longrightarrow \rho$$

acts as a pushforward from arbitrary data-generating mechanisms to a constrained family of hierarchical-separation statistics. In the idealized infinite 2-adic limit, the discrete distribution $\rho(Q_j)$ may be replaced by a continuum description $\rho(x)$ on $[0, 1]$.

Information geometry on the space of views distributions.

Because ρ is induced by relational structure rather than fitted as a free model, one may formulate dynamics directly as motion on the manifold of admissible views distributions. Following Fisher–Rao information geometry, a parametric family

$$\mathcal{S} = \{p(x; \vartheta)\}$$

is treated as a Riemannian manifold with metric

$$g_{ab}(\vartheta) = \int \frac{\partial \log p(x; \vartheta)}{\partial \vartheta_a} \frac{\partial \log p(x; \vartheta)}{\partial \vartheta_b} p(x; \vartheta) dx.$$

The Fisher–Rao distance is then the minimal curve length between two distributions, and geodesics $\vartheta(\lambda)$ satisfy the usual second-order equations determined by g_{ab} . In this framework, the curve parameter λ plays the role of a proper-time-like parameter for distributional evolution.

A four-parameter coordinatization of the admissible family ρ .

A central structural result of the earlier construction is that the family of views distributions induced by dendrograms can be coordinatized by four real parameters. The construction adapts Barbour-like “shape complexity” ingredients to the shape of the discrete graph $(Q_j, \rho(Q_j))$. Treating the distribution as a finite point cloud in the (Q, ρ) -plane, with points (Q_i, ρ_i) , define pairwise Euclidean separations

$$R_{ij} = \left((Q_i - Q_j)^2 + (\rho_i - \rho_j)^2 \right)^{1/2},$$

and pairwise weights

$$M_{ij} = Q_i \rho_i Q_j \rho_j.$$

From these one constructs four scalar functionals:

$$\hat{\theta}_1 = \sum_{i < j} M_{ij} R_{ij}^2, \quad \hat{\theta}_2 = \sum_{i < j} M_{ij} R_{ij}, \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{\theta}_3 = \sum_{i < j} M_{ij}, \quad \hat{\theta}_4 = \sum_{i < j} R_{ij}^4. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Up to equivalent normalizations, the point

$$\hat{\theta} = (\hat{\theta}_1, \hat{\theta}_2, \hat{\theta}_3, \hat{\theta}_4)$$

serves as a coordinate representation of the induced views distribution.

Within the admissible class generated by dendrograms, the working structural result is that these four coordinates determine the distribution shape uniquely. Accordingly, one may write

$$\rho \equiv \rho(\hat{\theta}). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

This provides the second parameter space used in the main text: while θ parameterizes dendrogram structures themselves, $\hat{\theta}$ parameterizes the views distributions induced by those structures.

Link to Bohmian structures via Fisher information.

The views distribution also provides the bridge to a Bohmian-like description. One may define a quantum-potential-type functional of ρ ,

$$U_Q = \frac{\Delta^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}},$$

whose expectation is directly related to Fisher information. In particular, the Fisher information functional

$$I = \int \rho (\nabla \log \rho)^2 dx$$

controls the mean quantum potential up to constants, thereby linking information geometry on ρ -space with Bohmian-like dynamics. This completes the chain

dendrogram $\longrightarrow \rho$ (views statistics) $\longrightarrow \hat{\theta} \longrightarrow$ (information geometry / quantum potential).

A.3 Views distributions as the bridge to the wave function

Building on the Minkowski-like parameter space above, where each dendrogram structure is represented by a point

$$\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4\},$$

we interpret *events* as interaction outcomes (measurements) generated along an observer's measurement history. In this broad sense, any interacting physical system may be treated as an observer in DHT: what matters is the acquisition of relational information through interaction.

From dendrograms to the views distribution.

Given a dendrogram encoding the relations among a finite set of events through p -adic edge codes, we map its branches to real event-values $\text{event}_i \in [0, 1]$ by the Monna map and define pairwise view-differences

$$q_{ik} = |\text{event}_i - \text{event}_k|.$$

The resulting discrete distribution of differences,

$$\rho(Q_j) = p_j, \quad p_j = \frac{|\{q_{ik} : q_{ik} = Q_j\}|}{|\{q_{ik}\}|},$$

is the fundamental probabilistic object. It records how relational separation scales are populated inside the dendrogram and serves as the starting point for the dynamical formulation and for the emergence of a wave-function description [5, 6].

Momentum-like variable and phase.

A key step is to define a momentum-like scalar from the views. One convenient choice is the mean pairwise difference

$$p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \neq j} q_{jk},$$

where N is the number of admissible pairs. In the same construction, one then introduces a phase functional S through the momentum–phase relation

$$p = \partial S, \quad \partial S = e^{iS},$$

so that the observer-dependent wave function takes the polar form

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{iS}.$$

This is the step at which the chain

$$\text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \rho$$

becomes

$$\text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \rho \longrightarrow \psi.$$

In other words, the dendrogram induces ρ , and ρ , together with the phase prescription, induces ψ [5–7].

Action principle and Bohmian-like quantum potential.

To turn (ρ, S) into dynamical variables, one introduces an action functional containing a kinetic-like contribution built from $(\partial S)^2$, a potential term U , and an additional “variety” term ν whose variation yields the Bohmian-like quantum potential. In the form used in the earlier derivation, the action is written as

$$A(S, \rho) = \int d\theta \left(\int \frac{dS(\theta)}{d\theta} \rho(Q) dQ + \int (\partial S)^2 \rho(Q) dQ - \nu(Q) + U(Q) \right). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Here ν is constructed from pairwise difference structure by averaging quadratic differences of views. In the continuum limit, its leading nontrivial contribution becomes proportional to Fisher-information-type terms in ρ , schematically of the form

$$\int \frac{(\partial \rho)^2}{\rho},$$

and its variation produces the Bohmian-like quantum potential [5–7].

A convenient summary of the mechanism is that, after expanding $\rho(Q+x)$ and $\rho(Q+y)$ around Q inside the double-integral representation of ν , discarding total

derivatives, and isolating the leading term, one obtains

$$U_Q = \frac{\Delta^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}},$$

with higher-order terms giving controlled nonlinear corrections beyond the Schrödinger limit [5].

Effective Hamilton–Jacobi and continuity equations.

With this structure, the effective Hamilton–Jacobi equation takes the form

$$-\dot{S} = (\partial_{\text{edge}} S)^2 + U + U_Q, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

while the corresponding continuity equation is written as

$$\dot{\rho} = \partial_{\text{edge}}(\rho \partial_{\text{edge}} S)^2. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Here the discrete “time” increment is interpreted as the difference between consecutive dendrogram states along an observer’s measurement history:

$$\dot{S} = S(\text{present dendrogram}) - S(\text{previous dendrogram}),$$

and similarly for $\dot{\rho}$. These equations are quoted here only as the effective dynamical relations derived in the earlier supplementary construction [5].

Schrödinger reconstruction.

Equations (A.3) and (A.4) may then be read as the real and imaginary parts of the Schrödinger equation for

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{iS},$$

so that standard quantum dynamics is recovered as the effective description of the observer’s evolving views distribution and its conjugate phase [5].

A.4 The observer’s subjective wave function

A corresponding *subjective* wave function is assigned to an observer through the measurement-to-geometry-to-statistics chain

$$M \longrightarrow \text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \{\text{event}_i\} \longrightarrow \{q_{ik}\} \longrightarrow \rho \longrightarrow \psi,$$

where $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n\}$ denotes the observer’s concrete set of acquired measurements.

Dependence on measurement history.

The subjective state is determined by the observer’s measurement history, so that one may write

$$\psi_{\text{sub}}(M) = \psi_{\text{sub}}(\theta),$$

emphasizing that what matters is the relational structure induced by the measurements, namely the dendrogram-space point θ , rather than the raw identity of the measurement labels themselves. In this sense, the subjective wave function is observer-relative not because it is arbitrary, but because it is constructed from the observer's own relational measurement history [5, 7].

Many-to-one compression at the level of ρ and ψ .

Because ρ is a push-forward statistic of the dendrogram's encoded relations, the map

$$\theta \longrightarrow \rho \longrightarrow \psi$$

is generally many-to-one. Distinct dendrogram points $\theta \neq \theta'$ may yield the same views distribution,

$$\rho(\theta) = \rho(\theta'),$$

and therefore, under the same phase prescription, the same wave function,

$$\psi(\theta) = \psi(\theta').$$

This statistical degeneracy is not a defect but a structural feature of the representation: ρ is a compressed summary of relational separations, so different relational microstructures may share the same quantum description at the level of ψ [7].

Ontic limit and worldlines.

In the idealized limit $N \rightarrow \infty$, each observer is associated with an infinite measurement history, equivalently an infinite p -adic decision path. This may be viewed as the observer's worldline through the dendrogram (minkowski-like) parameter space. The subjective wave function $\psi(\theta)$ then becomes the dynamical encoding of the observer's evolving relational knowledge along that worldline [5].

A.5 Objective wave function and an emergent many-worlds picture in the relational-information framework

The many-worlds aspect of this construction is developed in detail in Ref. [7]; here we recall only the minimum structure needed for the present paper.

Observers, worldlines, and objective properties.

In DHT, events are interpreted as interaction outcomes, that is, as measurements of one observer upon another. Since dendrogram structures are coordinatized by the Minkowski-like parameter space, a single observer may be identified, in the ontic limit, with a unique infinite worldline in that space. By the ontic Leibniz principle, two distinct observers cannot share the same infinite worldline, and conversely a unique infinite worldline specifies a unique observer.

An observer's *objective* ontic property is encoded by its infinite p -adic relational branch. Epistemically, this objective property is what other observers measure; subjectively, it is incorporated into the measuring observer's dendrogram and hence into the observer's evolving relational state.

Transformation of an objective property into a relational wave function.

Fix an epistemic coordinate θ in the Minkowski-like dendrogram parameter space, representing an ensemble of observers who share the same relational knowledge state. Suppose that all observers at this θ measure a particular observer OB_k .

The objective property of OB_k is encoded by a p -adic branch or ball. Writing a finite p -adic expansion with digits x_0, x_1, \dots, x_k , denote the corresponding ball value by Z_{B_k} . Applying the Monna map transforms this objective p -adic record into a rational number

$$q_{B_k} \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{Q}.$$

Each observer at θ registers the same objective value q_{B_k} , but incorporates it subjectively into its own dendrogram. Consequently, relative to the epistemic state θ , the observer OB_k is represented not by a single event-value but by a *distribution* of admissible event-values on the unit interval,

$$\rho_{B_k}(x; \theta), \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

From this distribution one constructs the corresponding *relational wave function of OB_k relative to θ* by the same procedure used in the subjective-wavefunction construction:

$$\psi_{OB_k}(\theta) = \sqrt{\rho_{B_k}(x; \theta)} e^{iS(\theta)}.$$

Thus, $\psi_{OB_k}(\theta)$ is not an absolute wave function of OB_k in isolation, but a relational one: it is defined only with respect to the epistemic coordinate θ , and therefore changes as θ changes. Conceptually, it represents the translation of an objective property into an ensemble of subjective incorporations by the observers occupying the common epistemic state θ . In this sense, the same objective property may admit multiple relational wave-function representations across different epistemic states, giving rise to the emergent branching picture developed in Ref. [7]. Conceptually, this picture represents the transformation of the objective property of OB_k into an ensemble of subjective incorporations by the observers at θ , i.e. an objective-to-subjective translation carried by the common epistemic state θ .

A.6 Terminological note

This note is included only to prevent common misreadings.

Dendrograms, views distributions, and wave functions.

These are three linked representations of the same relational content:

$$\text{dendrogram} \longrightarrow \rho \longrightarrow \psi.$$

Here ρ is induced from the dendrogram through event encoding and pairwise views, and ψ is constructed from (ρ, S) . The maps need not be injective: distinct dendrograms may induce the same ρ , and hence the same ψ .

Detached versus embedded.

A detached representative describes a component out of context and is used for collision-class bookkeeping. An embedded representative describes the realization of that component inside a host and is the object that enters the exchange construction. Bosonic/fermionic behaviour is determined at the embedded two-particle level, not at the detached level.

Observer dependence.

Different observers may generate different dendrograms because they acquire different relational information through interaction. In this epistemic sense, dendrograms encode observer-relative relational states.

Why “Minkowski-like”?

The dendrogram parameter space carries a causal classification induced by containment structure: timelike separation corresponds to exact induced containment of a smaller dendrogram within a larger one, whereas spacelike separation corresponds to non-containment. The space is therefore Minkowski-like in its causal organization, rather than because it literally coincides with physical spacetime.